

**The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform:
Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators**

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Deliverable Report 2.4

Deliverable	D2.4 Report on needs identification for new member states and Action plan proposed
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Contents

Introduction.....	3
List of Abbreviations.....	4
Engagement of new member states & candidates with NanoCommons tools & services.....	5
NanoCommons network expansion to new member states & member state candidates.....	5
Needs identification for new members states/candidates	6
Action plan for new member states/candidates engagement and dissemination of NanoCommons.....	7
Appendix	8
Email text for first contact to identified new member states representatives.....	8
Survey for specific needs for NanoCommons tools and services.....	9

Introduction

Deliverable 2.4 is part of Work Package 2 (WP2) 'Community building'. WP2 supports the overall objective of NanoCommons to deliver a sustainable and openly accessible nanoinformatics framework (knowledgebase and integrated computational tools, supported by expert advice, data interpretation and training) by building a nanoinformatics for safety community. It achieves this through bringing together scientists from different fields of nanosafety research to bridge the gap towards industry and regulatory stakeholders to collectively move forward the field.

WP2 aims to bring together researchers from all aspects of nanosafety research and to create a community that will embed their knowledge, expertise and interests to promote research and data innovation and societal engagement. To achieve this, NanoCommons needs to survey the community and identify the needs of the different stakeholders, and based on these needs to identify the means to meet these needs in a systematic manner, and to communicate these solutions effectively among the research and stakeholder communities. Key to this provision of community-driven services is the project's visibility at various scientific, industrial, regulatory and public events as well as its facilitation of two-way communication with stakeholders at these events. During these events, NanoCommons needs to significantly contribute by showcasing its services and results, and discussing the match between our services and the stakeholders and nano-communities needs. Other core activities include being part of organisational efforts for key nanosafety events and continuous assessment of the latest research and data developments and incorporating the most significant of these into the NanoCommons platform, thereby making the developments available to the nanosafety community via the Transnational Access (TA) component of NanoCommons.

While showcasing its services and results, the aforementioned two-way approach will lead to stakeholder feedback and an iterative process to improve and enhance the NanoCommons services by tailoring them to stakeholders needs.

The need for community building and knowledge sharing within the nanosafety community has been clearly expressed through the EU NanoSafety Cluster's (NSC) Steering Group (SG) and Plenary meetings.

Community building activities within WP2 are executed through a whole range of different actions, such as workshops, conferences and symposia attendance, organisation of training schools, webinars and social media presence.

The first phase of the project used existing networks and communities from project consortium partners which were historically mainly centred around the 'old' European Union member states. However, the DoA specifically asked for engagement with the new member states and member state candidates. Therefore, this deliverable focuses on the applied strategy to engage with representatives from the new member states, their specific needs and requirements with the NanoCommons tools and services as well as the action plan on how to expand this network during the second phase of the project.

Revision 01 of this Deliverable is a shorter, more streamlined version, as per the feedback from the periodic review meeting, and further updates on the intensification of actions in the second period will be provided in the 2nd periodic report.

List of Abbreviations

DoA – Description of Action

DMP – Data Management Plan

F2F – Face to Face

NMs - nanomaterials

NPs - nanoparticles

NSC - NanoSafety Cluster

SG – Steering Groups

TA – Transnational Access

WP - Work Package

Engagement of new member states & candidates with NanoCommons tools & services

NanoCommons network expansion to representatives from new member states & member state candidates

The starting point for contact with representatives from the new member states and member state candidates (see Table 1 for listed countries) was the Nanosafety Cluster compendium 2017 (please note the 2018 version was not available when this search was conducted last year in autumn 2018) as well as personal contacts within the project consortium (BioNanoNet network, Antreas Afantitis (in his role of NanoCommons project partner but also coordinator of NanoSolveIT, NIA Symposium 2019 (see deliverable D2.2 for details) and NanoFutures.

The NSC Compendium lists all the currently funded and active projects within the NanoEHS research area in Europe. Therefore, the compendium was screened for contacts from the above listed countries, which produced a list of 54 contacts in total (Table 1).

Tab 1: Summary of the *new member states* as well as *EU member candidate* contacted (number of individuals per country) based on information from the NSC compendium as well as personal networks:

Country	Status	No. of persons contacted	Response received
Albania	Candidate	0	No
Bulgaria	New	3	Yes
Croatia	New	2	Yes
Cyprus	New	10	No
Czech Republic	New	10	Yes
Estonia	New	1	Yes
Hungary	New	1	No
Latvia	New	2	Yes
Lithuania	New	0	No
Malta	New	1	Yes
Montenegro	Candidate	0	No
Poland	New	5	Yes
Republic of North Macedonia	Candidate	0	No
Romania	New	5	Yes
Serbia	Candidate	1	Yes
Slovakia	New	3	Yes
Slovenia	New	4	Yes
Turkey	Candidate	6	Yes

Experiences from previous projects showed that mass emails and/or very general surveys hardly produce any constructive feedback, hence the decision was made to send out personalised emails with supporting

information attached in an easy accessible format, limiting the amount of information but offering contact details for more detailed information if wished (see Appendices 4.1 and 4.2).

To support the establishment of contacts and enlarging of the network for potential users of the NanoCommons tools and services, the second part of this strategy was a survey to gather feedback on the actual user needs. This survey was centred around questions asking for participants background, industry/business/research discipline and area they are involved with, if the NanoCommons tools and services are interesting in principal and if so what their specific ideas and needs are so that the NanoCommons tools and services could be tailored more specifically to the customers' needs and market to ensure maximum use and applicability also after project life. This survey was open to the general public and project partners networks, but was also specifically sent to the new member states and member state candidates contacts.

A second set of personalised follow-up emails were sent out after the first TA calls went live, including links to the TA offers and application to trigger further interest in the NanoCommons tools and services.

Overall, this personalised strategy proved to be successful as the return on survey and contact was much higher than normally anticipated with a total of 22 out of 54 individuals answering the survey which covers 12 out of the 18 targeted countries. For an overview by country in terms of respondents, see Table 1. However, only one contact so far expressed an interest in follow up discussions and contact via a telephone conference (Sabancı University Nanotechnology Research and Application Center, Istanbul, Turkey).

The results of the survey – mainly areas of interest and specific needs – regarding the new member states and member state candidates, are summarized in the next section.

Needs identification for new members states/candidates

Because the establishment of the new network is very labour intensive and requires a lot 1-2-1 interaction, WP2 decided to split this task into:

- a) establishing the contacts and forming of a new network, and
- b) then using this new network to distil down specific needs and improvements of the current versions of the NanoCommons tools and services.

However, WP2 is still in the early stages of the network extension (new member states and member state candidates) with still some countries completely lacking any contacts. The majority of these 'zero contacts' (see Table 1) is with the *member candidates* (except for Lithuania the countries of concern are Albania, Republic of North Macedonia and Montenegro), where we plan to intensify our efforts in the second project phase. Our main focus so far has been on the identification of suitable contacts followed by strengthening of these connections. Needs identification so far has been limited to the more general results from the survey.

A summary of identified areas of interest and potential needs from the survey are given as a positive reply (i.e. interested in the subject or area) out of a total of 22 surveyed individuals:

- Risk Assessment tools: 17/22
- Online lab books: 14/22
- Data cleansing, mining and analysis: 13/22
- Experimental design for nanoinformatics: 13/22

- Modelling (statistical, mechanistical etc.): 12/22
- Data curation templates: 11/22
- Tools integration: 11/22
- Modelling tools: 10/22
- Online data repository and accessibility: 10/22
- Awareness of the data FAIR principal: 9/22 with the majority being very interested in more information on FAIR it might be useful to include an information leaflet on FAIR with a couple of links and example how they are used within the dissemination strategy for future contact.
- Software development: 8/22
- Data storage (hardware): 8/22
- QSARS: 8/22
- ISA-TAB: 6/22
- Omics: 6/22
- Ontology services: 4/22

It was extremely striking was that currently only 3/22 use data management tools with 1 using eNanoMapper, 1 using own DMPs and the last one did not specify the applied data management structure.

In the second phase of the project, efforts will be focused on a more detailed needs analysis, potentially by carefully selected F2F meetings and interviews which could and should also include tools and services demonstrations. Additionally, in close collaboration with WP10 on Training, and WP9 on Demonstration Case studies, a series of events will be planned in new member states (aligned with relevant conferences where possible) in year 3 of the project.

Action plan for new member states/candidates engagement and dissemination of the NanoCommons platform

Overall, the contacts who replied to the survey and the emails will be further engaged through personal email and phone contact. Once the project is in a more advanced state, personal visits including demonstrations to selected partners are used as a ‘mouth-to-mouth’ advertising strategy to facilitate a broad recognition of the project also beyond its life-time.

Again, the contacts who responded positive to our approach will be regularly updated on conferences, workshops and symposia. The NanoCommons partners who are going to attend various conferences will offer the possibility to get directly in touch with us for a face to face meetings at these conferences. Establishing a new network takes time and specifically when it involves people from lower income regions it very likely requires us going there for a visit and contact them rather than expecting them to travel to a lot of events to meet us due to potentially very limited travel budgets.

Once this first set of contacts are established and strengthened, we envisage a further extension of the network to contacts from their networks. For network extensions to countries where we have not had any replies – which were mostly from the member candidates – travel with a ‘NanoCommons delegation’ is very likely necessary to establish personal contacts which can then be further extended. This will be done mainly by targeted event attendance to be able to establish 1-2-1 connections which can be picked up immediately after return for follow up. We expect to have a solid network of 30+ members from different countries established by the end of year 3.

Appendix

Email text for first contact to identified new member states representatives

Dear Ms/Mrs/Mr XY,

As you might be aware, the EU H2020 project NanoCommons has started in January 2018. NanoCommons in a nutshell will:

- Deliver a sustainable and openly accessible nanoinformatics framework (knowledgebase and integrated computational tools, supported by expert advice, data interpretation and training), for assessment of the risks of NMs, their products and their formulations by facilitating engagement with the research community, industry and regulators, and provision of funded access to the nanoinformatics tools for Transnational Access.
- Constitute a framework of knowledge and tools to support assessment of the hazard of NMs, their transformation products and their formulations for use in advanced materials and product design, regulatory assessment of NEMs and modelling as well as education around NEMs and their application as key enabling technologies.

This will be done by integrating the Novel and Emerging Materials (NEMs) communities around an agreed set of approaches for data generation, data management and nanoinformatics these will constitute a framework of knowledge and tools to support

One of our tasks is to identify potential beneficiaries for the NanoCommons platform with specific focus on the new member states of the European Union to further involve and integrate them at all levels of the H2020 workplan. As you met my partner Lee Walker (from CEH – UKRI) during the last NIA Symposium and you are interested in the NanoCommons project, I am sending you some general information.

NanoCommons specifically aims to:

- Channel information and activities via Regional champions to ensure that opportunities within new member states are incorporated and facilitated to take full advantage of the tools and services offered by NanoCommons
- Dedicated events to support participation from new member states
- Specific workshops to assure the involvement of new member states
- Facilitate rolling calls for new tools and services (from EU/national projects) to be integrated with the NanoCommons platform.
- Support users in developing their products, applications or services with a Helpdesk to act as a contact point between Users and the NanoCommons partners to respond to User queries.

In order to better understand specific user needs and to design the NanoCommons services tailored to these needs we have prepared a short questionnaire: <https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/PK2KXWW>

Your participation in this survey would be very much appreciated as this helps us to create platform that will issue the needs of all our customers/users. If you feel you are not the right person to answer these questions, please feel free to forward this email and/or our contact details to suitable projects and stakeholders. If you have any other needs which are not listed in the survey and where you think that NanoCommons could support you, please, contact me.

Please see the attached file for a quick overview about NanoCommons. Please, do not hesitate to contact me anytime if you have further questions or if you require more information.

With kind regards,
Beatriz Alfaro

Survey for specific needs for NanoCommons tools and services

This survey was open for the general public but also specifically sent to the New Member states and Member candidates.

Questions asked as part of the survey
Full Name
email address
Affiliation
Are you part of any current national or international project
Which NanoCommons Experimental Design Service(s) would be of interest?
Which NanoCommons Data Processing and Aanalysis Service(s) would be of interest
Which Nanocommons Data Visualisation and Predictive Toxicity service(s) would be of interest?
Which Nanocommons Data Storage service(s) would be of interest?
Are you currently using any data management plan/tools/quality assurance for the data generated by your project?
Are you aware of the FAIR (Finadable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data principles and what the entail?
If no, would you be interested to learn more about the FAIR principles?
Would you like to be contacted, at a later date, by NanoCommons regarding the services you are interested in and/or when user calls are launched?